

as long yellow needles, m.p. 185°. (Found : C, 62.9 ; H, 4.4 ; N, 5.2. $C_{15}H_{13}O_3N$ requires C, 62.9 ; H, 4.8 ; N, 4.9 per cent).

When acetone dicarboxylic acid (one molecule) was treated with four molecules of acetic anhydride in the manner in which the dihydroxypyrrone is prepared (*loc. cit.*), the sole product of the reaction is the acid (V), m.p. 157°.

In the formation of the dihydroxypyrrone one molecule of water is eliminated from one molecule of acetonedicarboxylic acid, as such the preparation of the dihydroxypyrrone was modified since the publication of the paper (*loc. cit.*).

On addition of acetonedicarboxylic acid (one molecule) to two molecules of acetic anhydride instead of two and half molecules, the acid went into solution as usual with the evolution of heat. After allowing it to remain for 4 hours and seeding the dihydroxypyrrone separated as small shining plates. This was left overnight and the next day it was filtered, washed and dried ; yield however improved a little. In this manner 20 g. of acetone dicarboxylic acid gave 12.5 g. of dihydroxypyrrone.

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MOLAR REFRACTION AND THE STRUCTURE OF OXYMETHYLENE KETONES

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The values of the molar refraction of ethoxymethylene acetone and ethoxymethylene methylethyl ketone are recorded and the results confirm the structure assigned to oxymethylene acetone and oxymethylene methylethyl ketone on other grounds.

On physicochemical evidence oxymethylene acetone and oxymethylene methylethyl ketone are shown to possess the structure (I) and (II) (R = H) (*cf.* Kaushal, Sovani and Deshapande, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 19, 108 ; Joshi, Kaushal and Deshapande, *ibid.*, 1941, 18, 479).

The molecule of (I) or (II) possesses a conjugated double bond, and their molar refraction has been studied. Oxymethylene acetone is unstable and oxymethylene methylethyl ketone is a solid, m.p. 72° (*loc. cit.*). Hence to study the molar refractions their ethyl ethers have been prepared by condensing the crude sodio derivatives of (I) or (II) with ethyl halide in alcoholic suspension.

EXPERIMENTAL

Ethoxymethylene acetone (I, R = C_2H_5) was prepared by treating the sodium oxymethylene acetone (from 12 g. acetone, 20 g. formic ester and 5 g. sodium wire in dry ether) with 37 g. of ethyl bromide in 250 c. c. of absolute alcohol and allowing

it to remain for 48 hours. It was then refluxed on a water-bath for 8 hours with more ethyl bromide (10 g.). The sodium bromide separating was filtered off and the excess of alcohol distilled. The residue was shaken with water and made nearly neutral with dilute sulphuric acid and extracted with chloroform. The extract was washed with water, dried over sodium sulphate and on distilling off the excess of chloroform 12 g. of crude product were obtained which on distillation under reduced pressure gave pure ethoxymethylene acetone as a very light pale yellow coloured liquid. b. p. 74-76°/6 mm. [Found: C, 63·2; H, 9·2; Equiv., 110 (back titration). $C_6H_{10}O_2$ requires C, 63·5; H, 8·8 per cent. Equiv., 114).

It gives red colour to ferric chloride which deepens on standing. It is not acidic to litmus but gradually shows acid reaction to moist litmus due to hydrolysis into oxymethylene acetone (*cf.* Claisen, *Annalen*, 1897, 297, 1).

With aniline and zinc chloride it forms the *anilide* $CH_3-CO-CH : CH \cdot NH \cdot Ph$. as a gummy product which after purification melts at 247°. (Found: N, 8·3. $C_{10}H_{11}ON$ requires N, 8·7 per cent).

By keeping in contact with semicarbazide hydrochloride, sodium acetate and alcohol for 48 hours it formed the *oxymethylene acetone bis-semicarbazone*, which crystallises from alcohol and melts at 242°. (Found: N, 41·5. $C_6H_{12}O_2N_6$ requires N, 42·0 per cent) (*cf.* Wallach, *Annalen*. 1903, 329, 131).

Ethoxymethylene methylethyl ketone (II, $R = C_2H_5$) was prepared in a manner similar to ethoxymethylene acetone. Thus the sodium compound from 12·5 g. methylethyl ketone, 18·6 g. formic ester and 5·8 g. sodium wire, with ethylbromide (33 g. + 10 g.) gave 5g. pure ethoxymethylene methylethyl ketone, b. p. 79°/8 mm. If, however, after removal of alcohol, the residual liquid was worked without making the solution nearly neutral, the yield increased to 7 g. and the colour of the product did not change to reddish as in the former preparation. [Found: C, 65·2; H, 9·6; Equiv., 130 (back titration). $C_7H_{12}O_2$ requires C, 65·6; H, 9·4 per cent. Equiv., 128).

It is a thin colourless liquid with a pleasant odour, is not acidic to litmus but after sometime shows acid reaction to moist litmus due to hydrolysis of -OEt into OH. It gives a faint violet colour to ferric chloride which deepens on standing or on heating. On prolonged contact with semicarbazide, alcohol and water it gave a solid (m.p. 260°) in very poor yield.

Refractivity Measurements.

The densities of the double distilled liquids were determined by a small pycnometer at 33° using the formula :-

$$d_4^l = \frac{W'D}{W} - \frac{0'0012(W' - W)}{W}$$

where d_4^l , density of liquid at t° referred to water at 4°; W' , weight of liquid filling pycnometer; W , weight of water filling pycnometer and D , density of water at t° (at 33°, 0'9959).

The refractive indices were measured by Abbey's refractometer and molar refractions calculated by Lorenz and Lorenz formula using Bruhl's values of atomic

refractions. $M_D = \frac{n^2 - 1}{n^2 + 2} \times \frac{m}{d}$ where 'n', is refractive index ; 'm', molecular weight and 'd', the density of the liquid.

For *ethoxymethylene acetone* $d_4^{25} = 0.93018$; $n_D^{25} = 1.6075$ and therefore $M_D = 41.9$; formula (I, R = C₂H₅) requires $M_D, 31.04$.

For *ethoxymethylene methylethyl ketone* $d_4^{25} = 0.93876$; $n_D^{25} = 1.4535$ and therefore $M_D = 36.9$; formula (II, R = C₂H₅) requires $M_D, 35.6$.

D I S C U S S I O N .

Ethoxymethylene acetone possesses a simple conjugated system and as such it gives a pronounced exaltation in the value of its molar refraction. But in the case of ethoxymethylene methylethyl ketone, the conjugation is not simple as in the case of its lower homologue. Had the structure of ethoxymethylene methylethyl ketone been (I, R = C₂H₅ and CH₃ replaced by C₂H₅) *i.e.* C₂H₅CO-CH : CH-OC₂H₅, it would have shown similar exaltations in the value of its molar refraction.

It is therefore due to the methyl group marked with asterisk that the exaltations are not noticed even though the molecule contains a conjugated system. This is the effect of the methyl group in producing what Auwers and Eisenlohr terms 'Störung' or diminution of exaltations (Cohen, "Organic Chemistry", Vol II. p. 35) and every disturbance of conjugation by substituents diminishes the exaltations.

Hence oxymethylene acetone and oxymethylene methylethyl ketone are correctly represented by the formula (I) and (II) (R = H).

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